

THE CONSTITUTIONAL BALANCES AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE POLITICAL SYSTEM IN JORDAN - A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

This research work aims at identifying the importance and status of constitutional balances in Jordan and their impact on political life (a field study in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan), where the researcher will use the realistic inductive approach, relying on his extensive knowledge and research in several books and legal studies. Through his work in the field of law as a professor in one of the prestigious Jordanian universities, specifically in the Faculty of Law, and by virtue of his previous experiences in political and administrative work in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and through his follow-up, reading, and knowledge of the provisions of the Jordanian Constitution and its amendments, the researcher tried in this study to focus on the most important factors affecting stability and Constitutional balances and their impact on the Jordanian political system and the citizens, and how this system is contributing to maintaining the political, social and economic stability of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. The researcher concluded at the end of the research that the ongoing constitutional amendments and the legislator's sophistication and keenness to preserve the constitutional balances in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, have actually contributed to preserving the Jordanian political system, which contributed to the positive action to manage community resources and achieve internal and external security for the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and achieve the greatest public interests and work to reduce social contradictions.

Keywords: Constitutional Balances, the Jordanian Constitution, Constitutional Amendments, Public Freedoms, the Political System.

INTRODUCTION

The Constitution, as it is known in the accepted international definitions, is the supreme law that defines the basic rules for the form of the state (simple or complex), the system of government (monarchical or republican), and the form of government (presidential or parliamentary), and regulates the public authorities in it in terms of composition, jurisdiction, relations among the authorities, and the limits of each. The authority, duties and fundamental rights of individuals and groups and establishes guarantees for them vis-à-vis the authority.

In the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, the first Constitution was promulgated on January 8, 1952, during the reign of King Talal, and it consisted of nine chapters and 131 constitutional articles. It is considered one of the most clear textual Arab Constitutions based on the principle of separation of powers, respect for public freedoms, and the granting of the right to partisan and political work, and trade union organization of citizens as a form of the stipulated freedoms.

The chapters of the Jordanian Constitution stipulate that the state system and its system of government are representative, monarchical and hereditary, taking into account the rights and freedoms of Jordanians and their duties, considering the nation as the source of authority, the rights of the king, inheritance of rule in the Hashemite family, and the powers of the government.

The Constitution also established clear provisions for the legislative authority, both notables and representatives, and granted the council of Representatives immunity to enable them to exercise their legislative and oversight role.

Nine amendments were made to the Jordanian Constitution during the reign of King Hussein bin Talal, may God have mercy upon him. They affected 24 articles, and focused mainly on the legislative authority, from which powers were taken away in favor of the executive authority, especially expanding the powers to dissolve parliament and issue temporary laws in its absence.

Also, some amendments were made to the Constitution as a result of the occupation of the West Bank in 1967 by Israel, after it was part of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and before the decision to disengage from the legal and administrative ties with the West Bank, which was issued in 1988.

In 2011 AD, His Majesty King Abdullah II Ibn Al-Hussein directed to form a committee to study some of the proposed constitutional amendments. The committee worked to study the amendments and discuss their impact on the political system in Jordan mainly and on the economic and social system in general.

Subsequently, the committee handed over its amendments to the King on August 14, 2011, and they included the amendment of forty-five articles, the introduction of fifteen new articles, and the cancellation of many articles. The amendments mainly relate to strengthening the powers of the legislative authority, fortifying the council of Representatives and strengthening its role, stipulating the establishment of an independent election commission, and that appeals against the representation of members of the council of Representatives be before the ordinary courts.

It also stipulated the establishment of a Constitutional Court, the abolition of the Supreme Council for the Interpretation of the Constitution, the trial of ministers before the ordinary judiciary, and other articles that were considered a return to the 1952 Constitution to a large extent.

And the amendments kept the powers of the king, as he is the head of the state and the maintainer of order in it, so they kept giving him the power to appoint heads of government, but they re-restricted his powers to dissolve parliament and defined them with clear provisions through which the parliament is not absent for a period of more than four months, during which elections take place or the dissolved parliament returns in the event not holding elections.

Once again, the Jordanian Constitution was subjected to a new amendment as a result of popular protests and the arrival of Syrian refugees and others, which prompted His Majesty King Abdullah II to hold an emergency meeting in September of 2014, where Parliament approved amendments that contributed to making additional balances, as Parliament approved amendments that included public freedoms such as freedom of election and the freedom to form political parties. The amended texts also affirmed that the Jordanian family is the foundation of society and its basis is religion, morals and patriotism, and the law preserves its legal entity and strengthens its bonds and values, and that the law protects motherhood, childhood and old age, and takes care of children and people with disabilities and protects them

from abuse and exploitation. I also affirmed developing good citizenship and concepts of loyalty and belonging.

The amendment also included that every assault on public rights and freedoms or the sanctity of the private life of Jordanians is a crime punishable by law. The amendment also included that anyone who is arrested, detained, imprisoned, or whose freedom is restricted in accordance with the provisions of the law must be treated in a way that preserves human dignity. And torturing him it is not permissible in any way, or harming him physically or morally; moreover, it is not permissible to detain him in places other than those permitted by the laws, and every statement made by any person under the weight of any torture, abuse or threat is not counted, and the amendments included other public freedoms (that the state guarantees the freedom of scientific research and literary, artistic, cultural and sport creativity is guaranteed in a way that does not contravene the provisions of the law or public order and morals. It also stipulated that the state guarantees freedom of the press, printing, publishing, and the media within the limits of the law, and stipulated that Jordanians have the right to form political parties, trade unions, and associations.

In March 2016, another minor amendment was made to the provisions of the Constitution, as the comprehensive national plan for human rights for the years (2016-2025) was launched. It is considered a real methodology to activate the file of human rights and public freedoms in Jordan. In its contents it focused on the axes of civil, economic and political rights as well as the axis of the most vulnerable groups in society, the most important of which are children and persons with disabilities.

In the year 2022, the new constitutional amendments were approved by the National Assembly, with its two parts, notables and representatives, and these amendments were considered the title of a new stage for effective political participation by citizens and an attempt to involve young people in effective programmatic parties that have sound visions that are compatible with principles, values, and good citizenship far from extremism.

These amendments included some new articles added to amendments of some previous articles. In Article (21) amending Article (76) of the current Constitution; it provides for amendments that include: an endorsement to prevent combining the membership of the National Assembly and the Council of Ministers, an endorsement to prevent combining the membership of notables or representatives councils with any public position, and an endorsement not to include notables and representative in amending membership allocations if it was done in their time.

And Article (6) cancels the text of Article 52 of the Constitution and replaces it with the following text to read: “The prime minister, or the minister, or whoever acts on their behalf has the right to speak in the notables and the representatives councils, and to precede all members in addressing the two councils.”

And in Article (30) amending Article 128 of the Constitution, the article approved the deletion of the three-year period mentioned in Article 128 of the Constitution, which was granted to harmonize laws and regulations with the amendment of the Constitution in 2011.

The new amendments also stipulated that the government's resignation should not be approved when the parliament is dissolved 4 months before the end of its term, and an amendment was approved that prevents the representative and the notable from contracting, renting, selling and bartering with the government.

The recent constitutional amendments also approved the entry into force of the representative's resignation from the date of its submission.

It also stipulated the approval of the establishment of a committee of notables and representatives to discuss the disputed articles, agree on a final formula and submit its recommendations to the Council, unify the general budget in one law, and set a time limit for discussing the reports of the Audit Bureau.

Clause (c) of Paragraph 1 of Article 61 of the Constitution was amended, giving the decision-maker the power to choose members of the Constitutional Court from specialists (and not just one) who meet the conditions for membership in The Notables Council, with an increase in the period of service in the legal profession required for appointment to the Constitutional Court from 15 to 20 years, in addition to changing the name of the Supreme Court of Justice to the Supreme Administrative Court.

Article 64 related to the conditions for membership of The Notables Council was amended to include: former prime ministers, ministers, and those who held leadership positions, presidents of the council of representatives, presidents and judges of the Court of Cassation, the Supreme Administrative Court, the Supreme Sharia Court, the president and members of the Constitutional Court, in addition to retired officers from the rank of major general or higher, and the former representatives who were elected to the representation office no less than twice, and who are similar to these personalities who have gained the people's trust and reliance through their deeds and services to the nation and the country.

The amendments introduced new terms of reference for the work of the Independent Election Commission, which is to consider requests for the establishment of political parties, and to follow up on their affairs, instead of the Ministry of Political and Parliamentary Affairs, when amending paragraph 2 of Article 67 of the Constitution, which reads, "An independent body shall be established by law entrusted to administrate, parliamentary and municipal elections, and any general elections in accordance with the provisions of the law, and the Council of Ministers may assign the independent commission to manage or supervise any other elections based on the request of the legally authorized party to conduct such elections, and to consider applications for the establishment of political parties and follow up on their affairs in accordance with the provisions of the law.

And the amended Article 69, which determines the term of the presidency of the council of representatives to one solar year instead of two years, in addition to granting the representatives the right to dismiss their president by a decision issued by two-thirds of the members, and dealing with cases of vacancy in the position of the President of the Council, whether by resignation, death, dismissal, or for any other reason, through the vice-president assumption of the presidency of the Council until a new president is elected within a period of two weeks

from the date of the vacancy of the position. But if the Council is not in session, then it is called to convene in an extraordinary session in which it elects its president, to complete the remaining term of the presidency of the Council, in addition to considering the resignation of the President of the Council of Representatives from his post “effective” from the date of its deposit with the General Secretariat of the Council.

The amended Article 70 stipulated that the age of candidacy for parliament membership should be reduced from 30 to 25 solar years, with the fulfillment of membership conditions stipulated in the election law, to encourage youth participation.

Article 71 was amended, which assigns the authority to decide on the validity of parliament members’ representation to the Court of Cassation instead of the three courts of appeal.

According to paragraph 1 of the amended Article 71, the Court of Cassation has the right to decide on the validity of the representation of members of the council of Representatives in accordance with the provisions of the law, provided that the appeal is submitted within 15 days from the date of publication of the election results in the official newspaper, and the court must decide on the appeal within a period not exceeding 30 days from the date of filing the appeal.

Three clauses (g, h, and i) were added to the second paragraph of Article 40 of the Constitution, related to cases in which the king exercises his powers by a single royal will, which adds powers to appoint, accept resignation, and terminate the services of each of the Chief Justice, the President of the Sharia Judicial Council, the Grand Mufti, the Chief of the Royal Court, the Minister of Court, and the King's advisors.

And the council deleted item (j) added from the government, related to the King’s appointment of the members of the National Security Council and foreign policy, and it also canceled the word “Director of the Gendarmerie” mentioned in item (f) of the second paragraph, and replaced it with the phrase “Director of Public Security”, in addition to the text on the power of the king to accept the resignations of the army commander, and the two directors of intelligence and public security, in addition to the powers of “appointment and termination of services” mentioned in item (f).

Paragraph 2 of Article 40 of the Constitution, after the amendment, stipulates that the king exercises his powers by a royal will without the signature of the prime minister and the relevant minister or ministers, in the following cases: choosing the crown prince, appointing the deputy king, appointing the president of The Notables Council and its members, dissolving the council, and accepting a resignation or exemption of any of its members from membership, appointing the head of the Judicial Council and accepting his resignation, appointing the president and members of the Constitutional Court and accepting their resignations, in addition to appointing and accepting resignations, and terminating the services of each of the Army Commander, Director of Intelligence, Director of Public Security, Chief Judge, Head of the Sharia Judicial Council, and the Grand Mufti, Chief of the Royal Court, Minister of Court, and King's Advisers.

And the phrase “during his ministry” was added to Article 44 of the Constitution, after the word “minister,” and “government property” was replaced by “state property,” so that the article becomes: “A minister may not, during his ministry, buy or rent anything from state property, even if this were in the public auction, just as it is not permissible for him, during his ministry, to be a member of the board of directors of a company, or to participate in any commercial or financial business, or to receive a salary from any company.

And Article 53 of the Constitution was amended, by requiring the signature of a quarter of the members of the council of Representatives to hold a session of confidence in the ministry or any minister thereof, instead of the 10 representatives mentioned in paragraph (1), with the addition of a new paragraph No. (6) That requires any ministry to present its ministerial statement to the council of representatives, which was elected during her time, and to seek confidence in that statement within one month from the date of this council meeting.

Paragraph 2 of Article 54 was amended, which prevents the assignment of the prime minister, whose government the council of representatives decides to have no confidence in, from forming the next government.

The amendment added by the government was rejected by the National Assembly, specifically to Article 56, which allows the “non-working” minister to be tried directly before the judiciary, and to keep the article as it is, and thus not prejudice the right of Parliament to refer “working and non-working” ministers to the Public Prosecution.

The council of representatives crossed out the government amendment to Paragraph 2 of Article 59, which requires the approval of at least 25% of the members of either the council of representatives and notables when requesting interpretation of the provisions of the Constitution, as the representatives kept the condition that the decision be made by a majority of the members of either council.

Paragraph 1 of Article 60 was amended, stipulating that at least a quarter of the members of either council of representatives or notables must agree in the event of challenging the Constitutionality of laws and regulations in force.

And it was added to paragraph 2 of Article 60 that the courts may refer the “serious” plea of unconstitutionality directly to the Constitutional Court, without the need for another court to decide on its referral.

Paragraph 5 of Article 6 of the Constitution was also amended, in a way that enhances legal protection for persons with disabilities and enhances their participation, as the new amendment stipulates that the law protects the rights of persons with disabilities and promotes their participation and integration in the various aspects of life. It also protects motherhood, childhood and old age, takes care of youth and prevents abuse and exploitation. Whereas, before the amendment, Paragraph 5 stipulated that the law protects motherhood, childhood and old age, and takes care of young people and people with disabilities and protects them from abuse and exploitation.

It is worth noting that two paragraphs (6 and 7) have been added to Article Six of the Constitution to empower women and youth, as Paragraph 6 affirms that “the state guarantees the empowerment and support of women to play an active role in building society in a way that guarantees equal opportunities on the basis of justice and fairness and protects them from all forms of violence and discrimination,” while Paragraph 7 stipulated that “the state guarantees the promotion of the values of citizenship, tolerance, and the rule of law, and guarantees, within the limits of its capabilities, the empowerment of young people to contribute to political, economic, social and cultural life, developing their capabilities, and supporting their creativity and innovations.”

The existence of continuous constitutional amendments, which comes from legislative visions and a study of the Jordanian reality, has contributed to new additions and a solution to some contemporary problems as a result of Jordan being affected by refugee issues and falling into difficult circumstances as a result of what they called the Arab Spring in neighboring countries, and many internal and external issues, all of which have contributed to increasing constitutional harmony and balances. In every amendment there was an improvement and re-framing of some constitutional concepts and the addition of texts guaranteeing different rights and freedoms for citizens and residents on the land of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan in general.

We affirm once again that whoever studies the series of constitutional amendments carefully, and reads the contemporary reality throughout the past periods, finds that they are amendments to create solid constitutional balances that preserve the political system in Jordan, which preserves all their rights and freedoms for citizens and contributes to the security stability of Jordan internally and externally.

Research Problem

In light of the developments in the political life in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, which were affected by several internal and external factors, the constitutional amendments came successively and at different periods to strengthen the constitutional texts with the aim of guaranteeing rights and freedoms and a statement of duties and the organizational and administrative structure of state institutions. The researcher had to study the constitutional balances and their impact on the political system. In particular, the political life in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and this is what this study is focusing on.

Research Aims

The research sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Learn about the concept of constitutional balances.
2. Disclosure of the implications of having constitutional balances.
3. Knowledge of the foundations for achieving constitutional balances in general and the principles relied upon in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan in particular.

Research Significance

The importance of this research comes from the following:

1. The importance of the topic that the research deals with and its novelty.
2. The possibility of benefiting from the results of the research by the Jordanian legislator, jurists, and statistical departments that measure the extent of harmony and suitability of constitutional amendments with reality (constitutional balances).
3. It is one of the few studies, as far as the researcher knows, that deals with constitutional balances and their impact on the political system in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research adopts the descriptive analytical method of the Jordanian reality, as it provides a description of the Jordanian political system and studies the amount of constitutional balances resulting from successive constitutional amendments, in addition to studying the impact of these constitutional balances on the stability of the political system represented by the rights and duties of citizens, the role of national institutions in the state, their rights and duties, and the extent of security stability, the internal and external of the state, which was inevitably affected by these constitutional amendments.

The Concept of Constitutional Amendments

There is an important difference between amending the Constitution and changing the Constitution. Amendment is a partial change of the provisions of the Constitution, whether by canceling some of them, adding new provisions, or changing the content of some of them. Therefore, the amendment requires maintaining the same Constitution.

As mentioned in the introduction to this study, a number of amendments have taken place in Jordan to the provisions of the Jordanian Constitution. New provisions and provisions have been added to it with the aim of granting and defining some of the powers granted under the Constitution. Some provisions have been amended with the aim of controlling freedoms and giving rights to citizens residing in the land of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

These amendments were a necessary response to the developments in political life in Jordan, which resulted from Jordan's influence on neighboring countries, especially the refugee file during the period of what they called the Arab Spring.

The Concept of the Political System

The political system is **a social system that performs several roles or multiple functions based on the authority vested in it or the power on which it relies**, including managing the resources of society, achieving internal and external security, achieving the greatest amount of public interests, and working to reduce social contradictions.

It is also defined as a set of codified practices and behaviors, which play an important role in legally organizing the work of institutions and forces in a single society. Some political thinkers

and jurists have also termed it as legal regulations and rules that a country works to apply to the people who governs it, in pursuit of welfare, justice, freedoms, and security for the state internally and externally, and thus achieving the largest number of interests that are in line with the interests of the people, and the political decision-making institutions in the state are responsible for implementing this system.

Functions of the Political System

- It plays an important role in drawing the dimensions of society; this is in terms of goals and endeavors that achieve well-being and security for members of society and the state.
- Melting the energies of the members of the community within a crucible serving the community, ensuring the strengthening of the role of its people in the pursuit of prosperity and safety.
- It plays a prominent role in integrating the elements of society and adapting them to each other; this is in pursuit of the public interest.
- The political system gives legitimacy to the political life of individuals by applying the provisions and rules of law and public policy.

The characteristics of the political system

- It ensures justice and equality among the members of the same society.
- It is characterized by self-independence.
- It imposes its control over the relations that bind its elements through a set of rules and governing laws, thus the political system affects society more deeply and strictly.
- It is considered the main engine in any environment in which it exists, and it is also capable of interacting with other systems in society, such as the economic, cultural and social.

The levels of the political system

- Decision-making: this level of the political system is considered a means of making decisions in various manifestations. Decision-making may be represented by a political discourse, a constitutional amendment, or the rejection of amended laws. Official departments work on decision-making, they assume the same structure of law system, for the political system tries to consult with opposition parties and civil society organizations to be able to monitor decisions and verify them carefully in order to reach a correct decision.
- Implementation of the decision: the executive branch is represented by the ministries, states, municipalities, and government agencies. This level gives the political system credibility, and the non-implementation of decisions in the political system is considered humiliating to the political system.
- Marketing the decision: it is the entity responsible for the media, and it is an integral part of the executive apparatus. It is responsible for implementing the decisions issued by the entity that made it, studying it thoroughly and predicting its consequences and feedback.

The factors of stability of the political system in Jordan

A stable society does not mean that this society is devoid of problems and worries or that it is a society in which you do not criticize the government or the existing systems.

Stability in the political systems is a relative concept that describes the process of legal and peaceful transfer of power. Stability is linked to the absence of political violence and the existence of a stable political system that is governed by peace and obedience to the law, and decisions are taken according to predetermined procedures.

Historically, according to induction and those familiar with the situation, Jordan suffered from various waves of political instability in some circumstances and cases, but the regime managed to maintain its continuity and relative stability in a significant way, especially during what they called the Arab Spring and beyond.

Therefore, there are several factors that contributed to the strengthening of political stability in Jordan, including: the personality of the king and his political behavior, which is represented in the permanent reading of the reality of the situation in Jordan and the attempt to amend the Constitution and provisions accordingly, the role of the army and other security agencies, the prevailing social structures and the state of social harmony and the centralization of the system during crises. In addition, there are two more important factors, which are the high degree of political adaptation, and the increase in political awareness of the Jordanian citizen.

King Abdullah II represents the political behavior of the Hashemite leadership, whose legitimacy is based on multiple foundations, including religious legitimacy, national legitimacy (as a leader of the Great Arab Revolt), the historical legitimacy of the Hashemite family, its role in the Kingdom and the Arab world, and its ability to direct the Jordanian legislator to amend provisions and laws under the so-called constitutional amendments.

It is well-known that King Abdullah II has a strong political will for political reform and the development of the structure of the existing political system. Despite the volatile environment and the prevailing economic conditions, the King continues political reform measures in various aspects. The king is characterized by rationality, wisdom, and clarity in dealing with the vocabulary of reform, and accordingly, we will discuss two main factors for political stability in Jordan: the degree of political adaptation of the regime represented by achieving constitutional balances based on constitutional amendments that touch reality, and the high level of political awareness of the Jordanian citizen and the degree of his/her affiliation and loyalty.

Readers, experts, and those familiar with the political history of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan believe that the current regime has a great deal of adaptation, intelligence, and political acumen, which has led to relative political stability, and therefore the political adjustment factor is one of the factors of political stability of the Jordanian state.

The process of political reform began several decades before the start of the Arab Spring. Martial law was suspended since 1989, the eleventh parliamentary elections were held, and the regime began issuing the National Charter document in April 1990, which is a political

document that clarifies the political process and sets the general framework for the practice of political pluralism. The democratic foundations needed to build a democratic civil society, and it is a comprehensive intellectual and political framework that regulates the relationship between government institutions and society at all levels.

The leadership sought to establish a new legal system for the Political Parties Law No. 32 of 1992, the Press and Publications Law No. 10 of 1992, and other laws that form the core of political accommodation, along with the establishment of an independent anti-government body. - The Anti-Corruption Commission in 2006. This approach has continued despite all the imbalances and difficulties.

The Arab Spring prompted the regime to adapt more to the accelerating changes by undertaking many other reforms, starting with the amendment of approximately 42 articles in the Constitution in 2011, and the establishment of the Constitutional Court based on Court Law No. Law No. (15) Of 2012 establishing the Independent Authority for Elections.

This is in addition to Political Parties Law No. 16 of 2012. The National Integrity System was introduced in 2012, and the government is currently sending a draft law on decentralization to the council of Representatives in its extraordinary session held on 1/6/2015, as well as amending the Municipalities Law, and the draft political parties law for the year 2015.

All this leads us to say that the political adjustment in the Jordanian political system, which is represented by the constitutional amendments, leads to the constitutional balance that led to a high degree of political stability, and therefore the constitutional balance is one of the factors of the political stability of the Jordanian state.

Democracy and Political Stability in Jordan

At the beginning of the eighties, a third wave of democracy emerged, based on public freedoms, human rights, fairness, and justice, and the dissemination of basic democratic values such as freedom, justice, equality, human dignity, and the rights of women and children.

The mind of the Jordanian citizen has been affected by these values and with the increasing awareness of the Jordanian citizen, they have become relatively part of the system of public values and are dealt with daily, not to mention the role of educational curricula and mass communication in addition to the democratic transformation that the country has gone through since 1989 and what has been achieved. In this area in the legislative framework of the law and the renewal of structures and institutions as well as a slight change in the system of social values, in addition to expanding the base of political participation at the national and local levels, all of this has directly contributed to raising the level of basic awareness of the Jordanian individual.

The True Belonging, Citizenship and Political Stability

The Jordanian people are among the most proud of their country and political system, and this is part of the general political culture that depends on three dimensions: the cognitive dimension of the system and its components, and the evaluation dimension that is based on the individual's ability to evaluate the performance of the system's institutions, positively or

negatively. Affiliation is the feeling of belonging and popularity of the individual to his homeland "first and foremost" interacting with this place with words and deeds, and his willingness to stand by this homeland and defend it. Belonging is also the feeling of belonging to the nation, the people and the culture. This is manifested in "citizenship" and evidenced by the positive participation in all activities of society, the defense of the interests of the country, the sense of pride in this belonging, and the guarding of achievements and public facilities.

Moreover, loyalty is that feeling of devotion and allegiance to the political system wherein the individual feels loyal to the idea, believes it represents it and identifies with it. This factor is the essence of the Jordanian citizen, who contributed to increasing his political awareness and his full response to maintaining a state of security and stability and conforming to the principle of existence and continuity under the umbrella of national pride. Moreover, it is known that this national pride increases during periods of crisis, and therefore the awareness of the Jordanian citizen is high, not to mention that the political system enjoys a very high legitimacy based on historical, religious and national factors and continuous achievement. Based on the foregoing, it can be said that a new concept has been deduced as factors of political stability in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, which is the basic awareness of the Jordanian citizen, in addition to other factors.

THE RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS:

This research reached a set of results and conclusions, the most important of which were:

- The concept of the Jordanian Constitution: it is a set of basic principles regulating the powers of the state and clarifying the rights of both the rulers and the ruled therein, and laying down the main principles that regulate the relations between its various public authorities. The first Constitution was promulgated in Jordan in 1952, then some amendments were respectively made in 2011 and 2014 -2015-2016.
- Considering that the constitutional amendments that took place in 2014-2015 have a positive impact on the Jordanian Constitutional System, represented in considering them as an additional reform step towards achieving the full implementation of the concept of democracy and emphasizing public freedoms of all kinds.
- The concept of public freedoms, as freedoms are those that are prepared to be practiced within the framework of the state by the political authority to make their practice effective and real. They are "public", but they require the intervention of the public authority.
- The concept of the political system, its characteristics, levels and factors of its stability in Jordan.
- The constitutional amendments that took place in all stages came to address an urgent reality as well as local, regional and international changes.
- The constitutional amendments achieved eventually a constitutional balance and harmony with provisions and laws to maintain internal and external security and strengthened the stability of the political system in Jordan.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Research works should be directed towards studying and researching more about the factors of political stability and trying to help the state and its legislative, executive and oversight institutions with proposals and logical, implementable amendments that would improve the political system in Jordan.
- Focusing on the principle of decision marketing, so that committees are formed whose mission is to educate citizens about the reasons for decisions and amendments to enhance the concept of political adaptation, belonging and loyalty, in order to achieve a valid citizenship in the end.
- We should be working to include the constitutional amendments in the curricula of schools and universities; this is in order to familiarize the students with the constitutional development in Jordan with tools for analyzing the political reality and its requirements, an attempt made to inculcate these values and concepts among students from the early stages of their lives.

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